

Evaluating the GST Revenue Trends and Their Correlation with GDP Growth of India

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Reena Yadav

Assistant Professor
Department Of Economics
Jagat Taran Girls' Degree
College, (A Constituent
College Of University Of
Allahabad)
Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Economic growth and development is always one of the most important macroeconomic goal of any country. Government has responsibilities to raise the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services over a period. Governments are saddled with the responsibilities to maintain stability, equity and justified distribution of resources among the citizens. It is levied in all part of the world primarily to raise revenue for government expenditures although they serve other purposes as well. According to American economist, Richard A. Musgrave, the objectives of taxation are resource allocation, income redistribution and economic stability. It is very important that the taxation system is designed in such an appropriate manner that it doesn't lead to any sort of market distortions and failures in the economy. The present paper attempt to investigate the Dynamics of Goods and Service tax and Economic growth in India since it is implemented. It provide a comprehensive understanding of GST revenue performance & its association with GDP as proxy of Economic growth. The study was based on secondary data analysis. Correlation coefficient test and percentage growth rate were used as techniques of data analysis. The study found out the rising trend of GST revenue over a period of time since it is implemented from 2017. The study also find out the trend of GST to GDP ratio and examine the significance of GST tax to GDP ratio & Tax Buoyancy for economic growth of the country and reducing tax gap.

Keywords

Goods & Service Tax, GST to GDP Ratio, GST Buoyancy

Introduction

India's Growth Drivers

India is already on the path to developed economy, having outpaced Japan to become the 4th largest economy in 2025. India is predicted to become the world's third largest economy by fiscal Year 2028 expected to overtake Germany. According to World Economic Outlook, India's economy is now a four trillion dollar and will remain the world's fastest growing major economy (2025). This strong and resilient growth rate is undoubtedly ambitious, It is due to a combination of various factors like robust domestic consumption demand, rising capital expenditure, manufacturing resurgence, service sector growth, demographic advantages, growing capital market, and focus on structural reforms are some of main drivers of sustainable growth. However, India's evolving fiscal management framework is critical towards consolidation without derailing growth, the role of Fiscal consolidation efforts of India in ensuring fiscal prudence and long-term sustainability is very significant amidst rising global uncertainties.

Understanding GST as India's pivotal consolidation effort

Goods and Service tax is based on "One nation one tax" concept to unite indirect taxes under one umbrella and facilitate economies to be globally competitive. France was the first GST implementing country of the world. At present about 160 countries have implemented Goods and service tax with different implementing models. India is one of those emerging economies who has dual GST model. The goods and service tax plays an important role in India's Fiscal consolidation efforts. It aims at restructuring tax collection and enhancing revenue collection. It contributes to reduced fiscal deficit and positive impact on economic growth of a country. GST is generally considered a vital tax reform that has the potential to boost India's GDP in long run. According to government projection GST would increase India's GDP by about 2%. The idea of implementing GST in India was first proposed by the Kelkar Task Force on Indirect taxes in 2000. The objective was to replace the prevailing complex and fragmented tax structure with a unified system that would simplify compliance, reduce tax cascading, and promote economic

integration. It was finally implemented on 1 July 2017 in India. The goods and services tax is a destination based indirect tax levied on the supply of good and services. It replaces multiple taxes such as central excise duty, Value added tax, service tax, central sales tax and other states and central levies. It is a multi-tiered tax structure comprising Central GST, State GST and IGST.

Performance of Goods and service Tax in India

Goods and Service Tax in India has led to augmented government tax collection and transformed tax structure. The latest trend of growth in revenue collection through GST and its visible impact on GDP growth is substantial. Goods and service tax in India is evolved over a time. It has generally been viewed as a positive force for economic growth of the country. It has shown an upward trend of growth in tax revenue collected through GST with streamlined structure, broader base and improved tax compliance; it grew from 740648 crore in 2017-18 to 2208000 crore in 2024-25. The consistent rise in tax collection and number of tax payers shows the success of GST reforms in broadening tax base in India. GST has become the major source of revenue to government with GST to GDP ratio of about 6.86 % in India for Fiscal Year 2023- 24.

Objective of study

1. To analyze the GST revenue trend in India since its implementation.
2. To analyze the trend of GST to GDP ratio and GST Buoyancy in India.
3. To investigate the relationship between GST revenue and GDP (as proxy of economic growth) of India

Significance of the study

The study attempts to investigate the relationship between GST revenue and GDP growth contributing to existing literature on taxation and economic growth. The study findings can offer new insights into the dynamics of GST and GDP growth association. The study aims to provide empirical evidence to inform tax policy decisions and equitable growth. The findings of this research can have practical implications for policy makers, academicians, economists and business stakeholders.

Review of Literature

Shinde M, studied the impact and challenges of Good and Service tax on various sector of Indian Economy. According to him it has positive impact on the economy as it remove economic distortion and contributes towards the development of a common national market. **Rao Govinda M**, studied the underline gains from the implementation of Good and Service tax in India. In his working paper he said that one of those gains is from the abolition of inter- state check post erected to enforce taxes on cross border transactions and inter-state check pots erected to collect octroi and entry tax by local bodies. According to him one of the major problems with Indian Fiscal federalism is the institutional vacuum to minimize transitional cost of inter-governmental bargaining and conflict resolution, GST provide an institutional innovation for such a task (2022).

Paliwal U.L. et.al studies the impact of GST on tax income of India. It revealed that post- GST implementation, India's tax income has reduced GDP receptiveness. It also indicates that after GST there os some reduction in tax burden on consumers and corporations, This align with government stated goals for GST (2020).

Malini. R, et.al examined consistency in growth of GDP of GST implementing countries of the world. The study analysed the consistency in growth of GDP of ten (There are 175 countries who implemented GST) GST implementing developed and developing countries and found out consistency in growth rate of GDP of major economies of the world. the consistency in growth. The result revealed that the GST is a harmonized, simplified and unified tax regime, the unique features of this regime enables the countries to sustain their economic growth (2023).

The study by **Lakshminarayan J**, et al on the impact of Goods and service tax on India's tax revenue generation, GDP growth and sectoral changes in post GST period evaluate its performance in boosting economic efficiency and simplifying tax compliance. Their findings spotted both achievements and challenges related with GST implementation in India. The study investigate that GST has succeeded in making a unified tax system and facilitated inter-state trade, but its performance is subjected to regional and sectoral disparities. Some sectors still have experienced problems due to compliance complexities and varying state revenues (2024).

Methodology

Research Design and Methodology

The study is based of secondary and quantitative data analysis and it is descriptive in nature. It follows an empirical approach to observe the statistical association between GST revenue collection and GDP growth. The sources of secondary data collected in research study is sourced from various survey and annual reports of the Ministry of Finance, Government of India and GST council reports.

Table-1

S.No	Research Framework	Methods, tools and Techniques
1.	Research analysis & Data Type	Quantitative & Secondary data analysis
2.	Research Methods	Descriptive and exploratory in nature
3.	Research Tools and techniques	Trend analysis and Pearson's Correlation analysis
4.	Variables	X: GST collection Y: GDP growth

Analysis

Relationship between Goods and Service Tax collection and Gross Domestic Production: GST and GDP are positively intertwined. GST implementation has positive impact on the Indian economy. It has streamlined tax system by replacing multiplicity of taxes in India. Through increased tax compliance through technology driven procedures, it has enhanced the tax collection that will contribute to long term GDP growth in the country.

Table-2
Trend of GST collection in India

Fiscal Year	GST (In Crore)	Percentage growth rate of GST Collection	GDP (In Crore)
2017-18	740648	-	17090042
2018-19	1177369	58.96%	18899668
2019-20	1222116	3.800%	20103593
2020-21	1136801	-6.98%	19854096
2021-22	1488227	30.91%	23597399
2022-23	1807680	21.46%	26949646
2023-24	2018249	11.64%	29535667
2024-25	2208000	9.40%	32411406

Source: GST Statistics, Goods and Service Tax, GOI & Economic Survey

Result and Discussion

Parameter	Value
Pearson correlation coefficient (r)	0.9867
R square	0.9736
P-value	0.000005778

The study shows the positive association between GST collection and GDP of India from FY 2017-18 to FY 2024-2025 with 198.117% increase in growth percentage. The correlation coefficient (R) equals to 0.9867 between both variable (GST collection) and (GDP). The coefficient of determination equals 0.9736 and p-value is 0.000005778. **Hence null hypothesis is rejected.**

Table-3
Trend of GST to GDP ratio and GST Buoyancy in India

Fiscal Year	GST TO GDP Ratio (In %)	Growth rate of GST to GDP ratio (in %)	GST Buoyancy
2017-18	4.33	-	-
2018-19	6.23	43.87	5.57
2019-20	6.07	-2.56	0.59
2020-21	5.72	-5.76	5.6
2021-22	6.30	10.13	1.6
2022-23	6.72	6.66	1.5
2023-24	6.83	1.63	1.21
2024-25	6.81	-0.29	0.96

Source: Calculated on the basis of GST statistics

***Tax to GDP ratio = Total tax revenue collected /Gross domestic product of nation x 100**

***Tax buoyancy= % change in tax collection/% change in GDP**

***Growth percentage formula:**

Final Value-Initial Value/Initial Value x 100 Tax to GDP ratio

Tax to GDP ratio serves as an important indicator of fiscal health of a country's economy. It is defining as a measure of a nation's tax revenue relative to the size of its economy as measured by gross domestic product. A higher ratio shows that a country is generating tax revenue relative to its overall economic output, while a low ratio suggests the government inefficiency in collecting a significant portion of the country's GDP in form of taxes. Economically developed countries tend to have large tax to gdp ratio relatively to developing economies.

The GST to GDP ratio in India has seen a rise in recent years, showing improved compliance and resilient economic growth. In 2024-25 India's GST to GDP ratio reached 6.81 showing a marginal decline of about 0.29 % from previous year.

Tax Buoyancy

Tax buoyancy refers to the responsiveness of tax revenue growth to changes in GDP or National Income. A tax is called buoyant if the rise in tax revenue is more than proportionately in response to a rise in national income or output. High tax buoyancy indicates that the tax system is sensitive to change in economic conditions, whereas low buoyancy indicates that the tax system is inefficient or has structural flaws. The fiscal strategy of Indian government must focus on enhancing tax buoyancy and structural reforms to ensure sustainable growth. According to Srivastava, K India's current budget (2025-26) strategically balances fiscal consolidation with growth imperatives. In order to achieve a medium-term growth trajectory of 6.5 -7% and realize its Viksit Bharat vision, it must ensure tax buoyancy remains in 1.2-1.5 range, this would create necessary fiscal room to accelerate infrastructure expansion, enhance social sector spending and maintain fiscal discipline (2025).

Findings

1. There is a strong positive correlation between GST revenue collection and Growth of Gross Domestic Production in India.
2. The GST to GDP ratio in India has not been consistent throughout despite a rise in recent years. In 2024-25 India's GST to GDP ratio reached 6.81 showing a marginal decline of about 0.29 % from previous year.
3. The GST tax Buoyancy in India stood at 0.9 in 2024-25 seems fairly responsive to economic growth. Tax buoyancy of GST has improved over a year of its implementation. This shows not only increase in tax payer base but also lower tax evasion

Conclusion

The launch of the GST in India was a momentous indirect tax reform. It has significant positive relationship with economic growth of a country. It has significantly impacted Indian economic growth by eliminating two important constraints i.e. multiplicity and cascading effect of indirect taxes in India. However, in comparison to other big economies of the world such as France, United Kingdom and Italy the tax to GDP ratio is low. The study concludes the need of strengthening the tax system for enhancing the tax revenue performance in India. According to National Council of Applied Economic Research, Good and Service tax in India could increase the GDP by 0.9 % to 1.7 %, but its full potential can be realized only if tax administration policy and reforms will continue to make improvements where required such as simplifying process of tax compliance, facility and relief to small

scale businessmen, rationalized rate and integrating technology to avoid technical glitches.

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